

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article describes the role of digital technology in improving the quality of education in the current information society, the use of Information Communication Technologies in the application of digital technologies.*

Keywords: *technology, digital technology, information technology, development, education system, IT, Internet.*

Introduction. Digital technologies are used in all spheres of human activity, spread through information flows in society and form a global digital space. Today they are widely spread in the world, because our society requires updated information. Digital technologies are used in almost all spheres of public life. The central part of this process is the digitalization of education. Today, much attention is paid to the digitalization of educational processes, since the use of digital technologies is of great importance in the further development of pedagogical methods of teaching.

Computer technologies have penetrated and are penetrating all spheres of human activity. It is impossible to imagine any sphere that does not use electronic computing. The sphere of education is no exception, and the process of digitization is being implemented step by step. Moreover, computers are considered not as an additional teaching tool, but as an integral part of the integrated educational process, designed to significantly increase its efficiency. However, such modern technologies are not always fully used to solve educational problems. This is because information technologies have not yet found their worthy application in schools. Not all the possibilities of digital technologies have been realized in schools. Modernization of the education system expands the possibilities of innovative development of society. It is based on the implementation of new conceptual approaches to the development of education.

Now new educational standards allow us to introduce a systematic and active approach to teaching students based on the use of the latest pedagogical technologies aimed at developing certain competencies and universal educational activities. The introduction of digital technologies into practice is one of the most important areas of modernization. This allows not only to increase the level of training, but also to develop information competencies and reveal the intellectual potential of the individual.

Methodology. Over the past decade, school education has been gradually moving towards large-scale digitalization. Nowadays, a school classroom cannot be imagined without a teacher's computer, an interactive whiteboard and other computer equipment. Digital technologies and methods of collecting, storing, processing and providing information, data and knowledge relevant to the requirements of users of information and technical resources.

There are three structural components of digital technology:

- technical production complex; supply;
- organizational and methodological support systems.

Information technologies, using means of communication and information, allow people to be aware not only of the present, but also of past events. Digital technologies manifest themselves in the following forms. Analog technologies represent information in the form of a continuous random variable; Digital information technologies use a discrete method of representing information in the form of binary arithmetic. The digital representation of information is more protected from interference, including through communication channels.

Thus, information technologies and computer science are closely related to each other. Computer science is the science of methods, tools and technologies for their automation, creation and use. Computer science as a subject of study covers the content that forms the thinking of students. For example, these are the topics of “concepts”, “information structuring”, “reasoning”, etc. So, computer science as a subject of study is designed to form in students ways of working with information, thinking.

In computer science lessons, a systematic perception of the world develops, the assimilation of unified information connections of various natural and social phenomena, systematic thinking develops, the level of which is mainly determined by the ability to quickly process information and make informed decisions. This gives schoolchildren additional opportunities, and teachers the opportunity to use new teaching methods and tools.

The experience of teaching computer science shows that often computer science teachers do not realize the rich reserves of their discipline and do not set a goal to participate in the development of students' mental functions in the process of learning computer science.

In each school subject, digital technologies can be of great help, giving the opportunity to display graphic, audio and video files. In addition, there are a huge number of different programs with which you can comprehensively study object models and simulate any phenomenon or process, perform any complex calculations and provide detailed analysis. All this allows you to significantly save time, which is often not enough, allowing you to do what is often difficult or even impossible in real life.

Nowadays, information is becoming one of the main social values of society in the world. Information technologies have become an important component of the process of using information resources by society. Currently, they have gone through several stages, the transition of which is mainly based on the emergence of more modern technological tools for searching and processing information. The current stage of development is characterized by a shift in the direction of the information technology segment from the development of the technical base to the use of open tools to create a strategic advantage.

Digital technologies have entered our lives so rapidly that today it is impossible to imagine not only our daily activities, but also the development of all sectors without them. Naturally, as in all sectors, the introduction of digital technologies into the education system is also fundamentally changing its activities.

We are witnessing the extent to which the introduction of digital technologies into the public education system affects educational processes and what benefits they provide to governing bodies.

Currently, work is underway to implement digital technologies in two directions. The first is the digitalization of management in the public education system, and the second is the introduction of digital technologies in schools.

The second chapter of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy states that it is necessary to create a system for automating education management and comprehensively analyzing it using

modern information and communication technologies in the educational process. Accordingly, several systems are being developed to digitize the public system. A database has been created in this system, which facilitates the collection and processing of data from the bottom up. A modern method of entering, collecting, forming, and analyzing data has been established by creating an electronic platform in the education system. Understanding the advantages of using digital technologies in the education system and its perception by individuals is of paramount importance.

Results and discussion. In the implementation of digital technologies in schools, the role of educational aids is played by multimedia, overhead projectors, computers, laptops, Internet-connected televisions, telephone lines, smart boards, and projectors. Today, equipping the education system with them ensures high-quality lessons for students. Another advantage of digital technologies is that in the future, students will have the opportunity to receive education wherever and whenever they want, students will be able to choose subjects and receive education from home even in remote villages where there is a lack of specialists, and a culture of obtaining and using information from the Internet will be formed.

Also, in the second paragraph of the second chapter of the “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” strategy, it is stated:

- popularization of information technologies among young people, as well as development of skills in using digital technologies among all segments of the population;
- introduction and development of distance, online and virtual learning technologies in the field of information technologies, development of platforms for online courses;
- tasks have been set, such as making permanent changes to the core curricula of secondary schools in order to increase the overall level of use of digital technologies for students.

To make wider use of digital technologies, students must have the following skills:

- IT specialist skills for programming, application development and network management, and general skills for using IT for professional purposes;
- Additional IT skills for performing new tasks related to using IT at work, such as: information processing, self-direction, problem solving and communication;
- Digital literacy skills, as well as social and emotional skills that are crucial for ensuring the effective use of digital technologies by all people in everyday life.

They must also have digital literacy when using digital technologies. To have digital literacy, they need to have basic skills in networking, programming and algorithm development, communication and creation of digital products in individual or team work, knowledge of computer technologies, and the ability to use the web environment. They must know how to interpret and re-present information using information and communication technology tools.

Indeed, if we improve the quality of education, it will bear fruit in the near future. There are various ways to do this. We need to use the experience of developed countries and improve our own educational process, without limiting ourselves to our nationality. One of the necessary conditions for this is the use of digital technologies in the educational process.

This makes it easier for the learner to receive education by creating modern amenities. The role of the educational system in which digital technologies are introduced is played by multimedia, overhead projectors, computers, laptops, televisions connected to the Internet, telephone lines, smart boards, projectors. Today, equipping the educational system with them ensures high-quality lessons for students. The use of digital technologies in today's education system has proven to be effective.

Thus, the digitalization of education leads to changes in certain aspects of the educational process. The activities of students and teachers are being digitized. The student can use a large amount of various information, collect and process it. The teacher is freed from habitual actions and gets the opportunity to study the educational process and monitor the development of the student. In general, teachers are gradually moving from the established teaching methods in the educational process to the use of digital technologies. Computers are used mainly as additional educational tools. The use of information technologies helps to improve educational activities, increases the quality of the educational process and increases the effectiveness of individual activities of students. Also, the use of digital technologies in the educational process prepares qualified specialists in the development and application of modern technologies and tools for digitizing education.

Informatization of education means focusing on the new quality of education. The school is obliged to prepare graduates for successful life and work in conditions of prosperity and information. Information and communication competence, which was previously the property of a few, must now be accessible to everyone. This requires updated educational standards. Informatization of education is a process of change.

Analysis of modern directions of development of the process of informatization of education, its rational organization based on the interests of future scientific and technical, socio-economic and spiritual development of society is a complex and very urgent scientific, organizational and social problem. To solve this problem, continuous interaction of specialists in the field of education, as well as effective support of this interaction by the state, is necessary.

In addition to the main educational function, information technologies develop the creative abilities of the student and broaden his worldview. In addition to the main subjects, the student can receive additional education, for example, start learning a programming language, use online courses, simulators, communicate in any social network. Thus, the use of digital technologies in the educational process is necessary to prepare students for life and work in a modern information society.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that the introduction of digital technologies into the education system plays a major role in transforming the education system. It serves to organize modern education and increase the efficiency of education. At the same time, it ensures that we occupy an important place among developed countries.

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